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Experimental characterization and modelling of mechanical behavior of microcapsules in composites

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Experimental characterization and modelling of a single microcapsule

Micro photo of damaged microcapsules.

Analytical and FE modelling.

Force-displacement curves for the empty and filled with the water model system; experiment (solid lines), FEM calculations (dashed lines).

Mechanical behavior of microcapsules in composites

Example of prepared specimens before tensile tests.

Typical stress–strain curves for the polymer films filled with the different concentration of microcapsules.

FE mesh of one eighth of RVE.